

Environmental Research

Elsevier Editorial System(tm) for

Manuscript Draft

Manuscript Number: ER-15-1688

Title: The Cauliflower like Black Crusts: A natural passive sampler to evaluate the surrounding environmental pollution.

Article Type: Research paper

Section/Category: Environmental Chemistry & Modeling

Keywords: cauliflower like-black crust; sandstone; ICP-MS; SEM-EDS; HH-ED-XRF; μ -ED-XRF imaging.

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Abstract: Black crust in buildings can be formed as a result of different kind of chemical and physical reactions between the stone surface and environmental factors (e.g. acid aerosols emitted to the atmosphere, airborne particulate matter, etc.). Moreover, biological colonizations can also be present on them. This kind of pathology is widely present in limestones, but fewer are the case study dealing with the characterization of black crusts on sandstones. In this work we present an innovative methodology based on the use of Cauliflower like Black Crusts formed on sandstone material as natural passive sampler to evaluate the environmental pollution related with the emission of natural (crustal particles and marine aerosol particles) and metallic elements in the airborne particulate matter from the surrounding atmosphere. To illustrate its usefulness, different Cauliflower like Black Crusts growing in areas protected from the rain growing in an historical construction, La Galea Fortress, made up of sandstone and placed in the Abra Bay (Getxo, Basque Country, Spain) were characterized. This area suffers the anthropogenic emissions coming from the surrounding industry, traffic, sea port and the natural ones coming from the surrounding marine atmosphere. The applied analytical methodology began with a previous elemental in situ screening in order to evaluate and compare the presence of the metals trapped in black crusts from different orientations using a hand-held energy dispersive X-Ray Fluorescence spectrometer. After this preliminary study, samples of black crusts were taken in order to characterize them in the laboratory using molecular techniques (Raman spectroscopy and XRD) and elemental techniques (ICP-MS, SEM-EDS and micro energy dispersive X-Ray Fluorescence). With the last two elemental techniques, imaging analyses were performed at different lateral resolutions in order to observe the distribution of the metals and other kind of particles trapped in the black crust samples. Additionally, a

biological colonization found beneath the black crusts was also characterized using Phase Contrast microscopy.

HIGHLIGHTS

- Industry and maritime traffic have influence on the surrounding pollution.
- Cauliflowers like black crusts are passive samplers of environmental pollution.
- Molecular and elemental in-situ and laboratory strategy was applied.
- Globular/framboidal and flattest surfaces show different metals accumulation.
- Wind direction has a key role in the transport and subsequent metals accumulation.

The Cauliflower like Black Crusts: A natural passive sampler to evaluate the surrounding environmental pollution

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ABSTRACT

Black crust in buildings can be formed as a result of different kind of chemical and physical reactions between the stone surface and environmental factors (e.g. acid aerosols emitted to the atmosphere, airborne particulate matter, etc.). Moreover, biological colonizations can also be present on them. This kind of pathology is widely present in limestones, but fewer are the case study dealing with the characterization of black crusts on sandstones. In this work we present an innovative methodology based on the use of Cauliflower like Black Crusts formed on sandstone material as natural passive sampler to evaluate the environmental pollution related with the emission of natural (crystal particles and marine aerosol particles) and metallic elements in the airborne particulate matter from the surrounding atmosphere. To illustrate its usefulness, different Cauliflower like Black Crusts growing in areas protected from the rain growing in an historical construction, La Galea Fortress, made up of sandstone and placed in the Abra Bay (Getxo, Basque Country, Spain) were characterized. This area suffers the anthropogenic emissions coming from the surrounding industry, traffic, sea port and the natural ones coming from the surrounding marine atmosphere. The applied analytical methodology began with a previous elemental in situ screening in order to evaluate and compare the presence of the metals trapped in black crusts from different orientations using a hand-held energy dispersive X-Ray Fluorescence spectrometer. After this preliminary study, samples of black crusts were taken in order to characterize them in the laboratory using molecular techniques (Raman spectroscopy and XRD) and elemental techniques (ICP-MS, SEM-EDS and micro energy dispersive X-Ray Fluorescence). With the last two elemental techniques, imaging analyses were performed at different lateral resolutions in order to observe the distribution of the metals and other kind of particles trapped in the black crust samples. Additionally, a

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biological colonization found beneath the black crusts was also characterized using Phase Contrast microscopy.

Keywords: cauliflower like-black crust; sandstone; ICP-MS; SEM-EDS; HH-ED-XRF; μ -ED-XRF imaging.

1. Introduction

On the surface of building materials included in constructions, different kind of crusts can be found. Among them, grayish or black crusts can be mentioned. Usually these kinds of crusts appear in the areas less exposed to the rainfalls. The chemical composition of them can vary greatly depending on the building material where they grow up (e.g. marble, limestone, sandstone, etc.), the geographical location of the building and the environment where the building is located. In this sense, the chemical composition of the black crusts on a building located in an urban and/or industrial environment (Prieto-Taboada et al., 2011), against those located in a coastal (Rivas et al., 2014), rural environment (Török et al., 2011) or volcanic environment (Barca et al., 2011) can vary greatly. The anthropogenic emissions coming from maritime traffic (Martinez-Arkarazo et al. 2007; Prieto-Taboada et al., 2013), industries (Ausset et al. 1998) or road traffic (Rodriguez-Navarro and Sebastian, 1996) can also have influence in the composition of black crust.

The matrix of black crusts is made up of gypsum ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$). In the calcareous materials (e.g. limestone which main component is calcium carbonate), gypsum can be formed between the reaction of the calcium carbonate from the material itself and wet depositions of the SO_2 present in the atmosphere (Sarmiento et al., 2008). Considering that the concentration of this acid aerosol is higher in the urban-industrial environments, it is supposed that the black crust formations will be found principally in more polluted environments (Marszałek et al., 2014). The formation of gypsum crusts and by extension black crusts does not easily take place on sandstones. However, these kind of crust have been identified in calcarenite sandstones (calcium carbonate acting as cementing agent in the stone) or even in calcium-carbonate free sandstones (Marszałek et al., 2014). Apart from gypsum, different kind of airborne particulate matter can be

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75 trapped on its structure. Among these particles, natural particles emitted to the
76 atmosphere and coming from the erosion of the surrounding siliceous and calcareous
77 stones can be deposited on the gypsum crust. Apart from that, metallic particles emitted
78 from anthropogenic sources on urban-industrial emissions (e.g. road traffic, industry,
79 maritime traffic etc.) (Ozga et al. 2014; Barca et al. 2014; Belfiore et al. 2013) can also
80 be trapped in its structure. Moreover, in the buildings placed in marine environments,
81 salts transported by the marine aerosol can also be trapped in the gypsum matrix.

82 In the black crusts, the responsible of its grayish/black color are the carbon particles
83 (shoot) trapped in the gypsum matrix (Bonazza et al., 2007). Additionally, organic
84 carbon and organic pollutants such as polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, triterpenoid
85 hydrocarbons, etc. can also be present in the black crusts (Saiz-Jimenez and Hermosin,
86 2004; Ghedini et al., 2006). Therefore, black crust located in urban-industrial
87 environments can act as repositories of inorganic and organic pollutants acting as
88 passive samplers useful to evaluate the pollution of the specific environment where they
89 grow up.

90 Although black crust is a well-known pathology in construction, in some cases, these
91 kinds of crusts can act as protective layer of porous building materials or as barriers
92 against the environmental stressors, which can react with the original material,
93 promoting its degradation (Török, 2003). However, in some cases, these crusts can also
94 have a destructive effect on the material, promoting for example exfoliations in the
95 original stone (Zhang et al., 2013). Apart from possible physical damages on the
96 material, black crusts usually give rise to aesthetical problems. During a restoration
97 process of a specific building, construction, monument, etc. in where black crusts are
98 present, it can be decided to remove these unsightly patinas. Two possible situations
99 could happen if these crusts are removed from its support or stone matrix. On the one
100 hand, a quick formation of a new gypsum crust on the stone could take place, slowing
101 down its deterioration process (Smith et al., 2003). The formation of this new crust
102 depends on numerous factors such as possible wetting-drying or freeze-thaw cycles that
103 can undergo the stone (Smith et al., 2002) among others. On the other hand, the removal
104 of the black crusts acting as a protective layer of the porous stone could make this
105 material very unstable (Török, 2002) in a short period of time, promoting its quick
106 deterioration (e.g. losing material).

107 According to literature, several works can be found dealing with the chemical variations
108 of black crusts compositions through times, depending on the changes in the pollution
109 levels (acid gases emission and particulate matter) of the atmosphere where the black
110 crusts are present (Barca et al., 2014; La Russa et al., 2013). Moreover there are some
111 studies which determine if the gypsum present in the black crust comes from a natural
112 origin or if it is formed due to the influence of wet SO₂ depositions from the
113 atmosphere. In those works, sulfur and oxygen isotopes analyses were conducted (Rivas
114 et al., 2014).

115 Generally, the analytical methodologies applied up to now to characterize the
116 composition of black crusts and the inorganic and organic pollutants accumulated on
117 them compromise a combination of different elemental and molecular techniques.
118 Several examples of multianalytical methodologies can be found in the literature.
119 Among others, the combined use of SEM-EDS with FTIR on the characterization of
120 black crusts on granites (Pozo-Antonio et al., 2015); ion chromatography applied
121 together with SEM-EDS in the analysis of black crust formed on dolomitic rocks in a
122 building of Milan (Fermo et al., 2015); FT-IR and SEM-EDS combined with LA-ICP-
123 MS in black crusts formed on buildings from Milan and Florence and monument from
124 Rome (Barca et al., 2014); XRD, SEM, TG/DTA together with ICP-OES, ICP-MS and
125 INAA analyses on black crusts formed on sandstones from buildings in Kraków
126 (Marszałek et al., 2014); FT-IR imaging combined with SEM-EDS and LA-ICP-MS
127 analyses on black crusts formed on building from Seville (Ruffolo et al., 2015); optical
128 microscopy, XRF, XRF, SEM, SEM-EDX, SEM-WDS, LA-ICP-MS, ion
129 chromatography and GC-MS techniques applied to characterize the black crusts from
130 the Cologne, Altenberg and Xanten cathedrals (Graue et al., 2013) etc., mutianalytical
131 methodologies can be mentioned.

132 In this work we present an innovative methodology based on the use of cauliflower like
133 black crusts formed on sandstone material as natural passive sampler to evaluate the
134 environmental pollution related with the emission of natural (crustal particles and
135 marine aerosol particles) and metallic elements in the airborne particulate matter from
136 the surrounding atmosphere. To illustrate its usefulness, different cauliflower like black
137 crusts growing in areas protected from the rain growing in an old building used to house
138 the lighthouse keeper from La Galea Fortress, an historical construction made up of
139 sandstone and placed in the Abra Bay (Getxo, Basque Country, Spain) were

140 characterized. This area suffers the anthropogenic emissions coming from the
141 surrounding industry, traffic, sea port and the natural ones coming from the surrounding
142 marine atmosphere. The applied analytical methodology began with a preliminary
143 screening of the black crusts was conducted using a hand-held energy dispersive X-Ray
144 Fluorescence spectrometer (HH-ED-XRF). After that, samples of black crust were
145 taken in order to characterize them in the laboratory using molecular techniques (Raman
146 spectroscopy and XRD) and elemental techniques (ICP-MS, SEM-EDS and micro
147 energy dispersive X-Ray Fluorescence (μ -ED-XRF)). With the last two elemental
148 techniques, imaging analyses were performed at different lateral resolutions in order to
149 observe the distribution of the metals and other kind of particles trapped in the black
150 crust samples. Additionally, Phase Contrast microscopy was used to determine the
151 nature of the main colonizer from the biological colonization found underneath the
152 black crusts.

153 **2. Materials and methods**

154 *2.1. La Galea site description and surrounded climatology*

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158 La Galea Fortress is located in the cliff overlooking the bay of Agra, in Getxo (Biscay,
159 Basque Country, north of Spain) and about 50 m above the sea level (see Fig.1). In its
160 origins (18th century), this construction acted as a fortress. This fortress undergoes two
161 destructions and after that, in the year 1782, the fortress was reused as a lighthouse. The
162 first lighthouse was substituted by a second one. In the year 1880, the lighthouse keeper
163 house, where the black crust objects of research are place, was constructed. Additional
164 description about the history of this construction and environmental conditions of the
165 place where it is located can be found elsewhere (Morillas et al., 2015).

166 167 *2.2. Samplings*

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169 Black crusts on the sandstone from the lighthouse keeper house are only present in the
170 South-southeast (SSE) and Southwest (SW) orientations. The SSE orientation matches
171 with one preferential direction of the wind in La Galea Fortress. In the NW orientation
172 of the lighthouse keeper house, very close to the second preferential direction of the
173 wind (North-northwest), black crust remains cannot be found. In the Fig. 1, a complete
174 view of the house under study, and the three areas where the in situ measurements and
175 sampling was conducted, can be observed. In the SW orientation, one sample was

176 extracted from the frame of the door (BC1). Two additional samples were extracted
177 from the SSE orientation, one of them from the frame of the door (BC2) and the other
178 sample was a compound sample formed by a mixture of two fragments from both the
179 frame of both windows of the SSE orientation (BC3). All the samples were extracted
180 using a scalpel and the size of the black crust fragments never exceeded 2-3 cm.

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182 *2.3. Instrumentation*

183 *2.3.1. Molecular characterization*

184 For the molecular characterization of the black crust matrix, a portable innoRam™
185 (B&WTEK_{INC.}, Newark, USA) Raman spectrometer was used in the laboratory. This
186 portable Raman spectrometer utilizes a 785 nm excitation laser and has a maximum
187 output power of 300 mW. Variable attenuation of the output power was achieved
188 through the implementation of filters, which allowed reducing the output power down to
189 1% of the maximum power of the laser. The measurements were conducted in the
190 microscopic scale thanks to the coupling of the Raman probe to the BAC151B video
191 microscope sampling system (B&WTEK_{INC.}, Newark, USA), which allows to couple
192 different magnification objective lens. In this case, the measurements were performed
193 using the 50x objective lens. The spectra were typically collected using a wavelength
194 range of 100–2200 cm⁻¹, although in some measurements larger ranges were used. The
195 exposure time for each spectrum ranged from 2 to 10 s, and two to fifteen repeated
196 acquisitions were averaged to improve the signal-to-noise ratio. Apart from micro-
197 Raman measurements, XRD analyses were performed with a powder diffractometer
198 PANalytical Xpert PRO, equipped with a copper tube ($\lambda_{\text{CuK}\alpha\text{media}} = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$, $\lambda_{\text{CuK}\alpha 1} =$
199 1.54060 \AA , $\lambda_{\text{CuK}\alpha 2} = 1.54439 \text{ \AA}$), vertical goniometer (Bragg-Brentano geometry),
200 programmable divergence aperture, automatic interchange of samples, secondary
201 monochromator from graphite and PixCel detector. The measurement conditions were
202 40 kV and 40 mA, with an angular range (2θ) scanned between 5 and 70°. For the data
203 treatment of the diffractograms and the identification of the mineral phases present, the
204 specific software Xpert HighScore (PANalytical) in combination with the specific
205 powder diffraction file database (International Centre for Diffraction Data - ICDD,
206 Pennsylvania, USA) was used.

207 *2.3.2. Elemental characterization*

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208 The preliminary elemental screening of the black crust was carried out using an
209 XMET5100 (Oxford Instruments, UK) hand-held energy dispersive X-Ray
210 Fluorescence spectrometer (HH-ED-XRF). The instrument is equipped with a Rh tube
211 working at a maximum voltage of 45 KV. The size of the emitted X-Ray beam is 9 mm.
212 The analyzer includes a silicon drift detector (SDD) of high resolution that is able to
213 provide an energetic resolution of 150 eV (calculated for the Mn K_{α} line at -20 °C)
214 which allows to acquire spectra with 20 eV resolution. The analyzer contains a PDA to
215 control the spectrometer and also to save the spectral and quantitative information. In
216 order to determine possible contributions from detector materials and possible
217 contaminations of the XRF analyzer window, 20 repetitive spectra of an instrumental
218 blank (a PTFE block) were acquired before each measurements batch. The PTFE block
219 was cleaned before its use in a 20% nitric acid bath during 24 hours. Before its use, it
220 was rinsed in Milli-Q water and dried. For the repetitive measurements, the same
221 spectral conditions (voltage, current, filter and test time) as those used for the analysis
222 of the sandstone were considered. To determine the presence of the heaviest elements (Z
223 $>$ Ti), and the voltage and current of the X-Ray tube was set at 40 kV and 15 μ A
224 respectively and the spectra were acquired during 200 seconds (real time) in order to
225 improve the limit of detection for the identification of trace elements. Additionally, to
226 remove the “pinches” Bremsstrahlung and 3rd Generation peaks, a 500 μ m Al filter was
227 used. In order to improve the detection of the lighter elements ($Z <$ Ti), additional
228 measurements were performed without the Al filter and at lower voltage (13 kV) and
229 higher current (40 μ A). The test time in this case was 140 seconds for each
230 measurement. All the collected spectra were transferred from the PDA of the instrument
231 to a computer in .txt files.

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232 For the characterization of the black crusts in the laboratory at millimeter scale, the M4
233 TORNADO (Bruker Nano GmbH, Berlin, Germany) energy dispersive X-Ray
234 Fluorescence spectrometers (ED-XRF) was used. With this instrument, punctual
235 measurements from the black crusts samples were obtained. The X-Ray tube
236 implemented in this instrument is a micro-focus side window Rh tube powered by a
237 low-power HV generator and cooled by air. Thanks to the collimator implemented, spot
238 sizes of 1 mm were measured. The X-ray tube can work at a maximum voltage of 50 kV
239 and at a maximum current of 700 μ A, which were the considered conditions for the
240 spectra acquisition in this work. The detection of the fluorescence radiation was
241 performed by an XFlash[®] silicon drift detector with 30mm² sensitive areas and energy

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242 resolution of 145eV for Mn-K α . In order to improve the detection of the lightest
243 elements ($Z > 11$), filters were not used and measurements were acquired under vacuum
244 (20 bar). To achieve the vacuum, a diaphragm pump MV 10 N VARIO-B was used.
245 The live time used for each punctual measurement was 200 seconds. For the focusing of
246 the area under study, two video-microscopes were used, one of them to explore the
247 sample under a low magnification (1 cm² areas), and the other one to perform the final
248 focusing (1 mm² areas). The spectral data acquisition and treatment was performed
249 using the M4 TORNADO software and the quantification was done thanks to the M-
250 Quant software package.

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251 For the study of elements distribution on the black crust samples, elemental imaging
252 was conducted using the portable ARTAX μ -ED-XRF from Röntec (currently Bruker
253 Nano GmbH, Berlin, Germany). The elemental maps were obtained using 650 μ m of
254 lateral resolution thanks to the use of a lower diameter collimator. Each elemental map
255 was constructed according to the net areas of XRF lines. The spectrometer implements a
256 low-power metal-ceramic-type MCBM 50 X-Ray tube with molybdenum target as
257 excitation source. The molybdenum can be used at a maximum voltage of 50 kV and at
258 a maximum current of 700 μ A (maximum power of 35 W). The radiation-protecting
259 tube housing is equipped with an electrical shutter and safety functions externally
260 controlled by a PC. The X-Ray Fluorescence radiation is detected by means of an
261 electro-thermally cooled Xflash[®] detector, which is a silicon drift detector with high-
262 speed low-noise electronics. The detector has an active area of 5 mm² and a 8 μ m-thick
263 Dura-beryllium window. The geometry between primary beam, sample, and detector is
264 fixed at 0°/40° relative to the perpendicular of the sample surface. The X-Rays were
265 collimated by a tantalum collimator with a diameter of 0.65 mm and the beam diameter
266 in the sample surface is around 200 mm². An integrated CCD camera provides an image
267 of the sample region under investigation (8 mm x 8 mm). In the vibration-damped
268 swivel arm from the instrument, a motor-driven XYZ positioning stage is directly
269 mounted, which consists of three equal modules with a maximum travel of 50 mm in
270 each direction. This motor unit allows focusing on different parts of the sample. For the
271 mappings and for each analyzed point, the maximum voltage and current and 800
272 seconds of test time were used. In this case, measurements were performed at air.
273 Instrument control and data-handling were performed using the Windows-base ARTAX
274 software 4.9.13.2 (Intax GmbH, Berlin, Germany). In order to improve the
275 representation of the elements distribution on the black crusts samples, the elemental

276 maps presented in this work were constructed using the Surfer[®] 10 software (Golden
277 Software, LLC, USA).

278 In order to characterize the particles trapped in the black crust samples, a scanning
279 electron microscope coupled to an energy dispersive X-Ray spectrometer (SEM-EDS)
280 was used. The SEM used was an EVO[®]40 Scanning Electron Microscope (Carl Zeiss
281 NTS GmbH, Germany) and the EDS was an X-Max Energy-Dispersive X-ray
282 spectrometer (Oxford Instruments, Abingdon, Oxfordshire, United Kingdom). In order
283 to improve the images acquired with the SEM, some samples were coated with gold.
284 These images were obtained at high vacuum employing an acceleration voltage of
285 30 kV and a 10–400 µm working distance. To take the images, different magnifications
286 (reaching up to 6,800×) were used by a secondary electron detector whereas an
287 integration time of 50 s was employed to improve the signal to noise ratio. The EDS
288 spectra were acquired and treated using the INCA software. This software allows to
289 analyze selected areas previously seen by SEM. Furthermore, a mapping of specific
290 microscopic areas in the samples was possible, allowing the evaluation of the
291 distribution of these elements over the samples.

292 ICP-MS was also used to quantify the major, minor and trace elements present in the
293 black crust samples. Prior to the elemental measurements, acid digestions of the black
294 crusts samples were carried out. For that purpose, black crust were crushed in an agate
295 mortar and dried until constant weight. 0.5 gr of dried black crust samples were digested
296 in a microwave oven using 12 ml of 3:1 HNO₃ (69%) : HCl (36%) mixture. The acid
297 concentration of the obtained acid extracts was reduced to less than 1% HNO₃ using
298 Milli-Q water. In addition, a solution containing 10 µg.L⁻¹ of Be, Sc, Ge, In, Re and Bi
299 was added as internal standard. The internal standards and ICP-MS calibration
300 standards solutions were prepared from 1000 mg·L⁻¹ stock solutions of Alfa Aesar
301 (Specpure[®], Plasma standard solution, Germany) inside a class 100 clean room. All
302 solutions were prepared using Milli-Q quality water. The elemental analysis of the
303 extracts was performed by ICP-MS (NexION 300, Perkin Elmer) in a class 100 clean
304 room. ²⁷Al, ⁴⁴Ca, ⁸⁸Sr, ⁹⁸Mo, ¹¹⁴Cd, ¹²⁰Sn, ¹²¹Sb, ¹³⁸Ba, ¹⁸⁴W, ²⁰²Hg and,
305 ²⁰⁶Pb+²⁰⁷Pb+²⁰⁸Pb isotopes were determined in standard mode and ²³Na, ²⁴Mg, ³⁹K, ⁴⁷Ti,
306 ⁵¹V, ⁵²Cr, ⁵⁵Mn, ⁵⁶Fe, ⁵⁹Co, ⁶⁰Ni, ⁶⁵Cu, ⁶⁶Zn, ⁷⁵As, ¹¹¹Cd isotopes were determined in
307 collision mode with He with in order to eliminate possible polyatomic interferences.
308 The plasma conditions such as argon flow of nebulizer, the torch position and the

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309 instrument lenses voltages were optimized before each measurement session aspirating
310 a standard solution of 1ng/mL of Mg, Rh, In, Ba, Pb and U. The gas nebulizer flow was
311 optimized obtaining a compromise between sensitivity and low oxides level (less than
312 2.5 % for the CeO/Ce ratio). Finally, the data were acquired and analyzed for the
313 element quantitative analysis using the Elan 3.2 software (Perkin Elmer SCIEXTM,
314 Ontario, Canada).

315 To determine the nature of the main colonizer of the colonization underneath the black
316 crust and on the sandstone, microscopic observations were carried out using a Nikon
317 Eclipse 80i PCM (Phase Contrast microscope) provided with 20×, 40×, and 60×
318 objective lenses. For the preparative process of the sample, special tweezers were used
319 to sample the main colonizer from the biological patina, under the view of a
320 microscope. After the extraction of the main colonizer, it was placed on a slide and a
321 drop of oil was also added to avoid spherical aberration with the highest numerical
322 aperture lenses, promoted by the different indexes of refraction of the specimen and the
323 objective lenses.

324 325 **3. Results and discussion**

326 327 *3.1. In situ elemental screening of black crusts*

328 All the black crusts present in the lighthouse keeper house are placed in the most
329 protected areas from the rain, that is, in the frames of the doors and windows from both
330 orientations (SW and SSE). Usually, dark coloured crusts tend to be formed in areas
331 protected from the rain. However, these areas are also exposed to the high pollution
332 sources (maritime port and industries) located near the building, allowing the deposition
333 of particles that are incorporated or trapped into the growing crust. In order to evaluate
334 if metals are accumulated in black crusts from both orientations, a rapid screening with
335 a hand-held energy dispersive X-Ray Fluorescence spectrometer (HH-ED-XRF) was
336 conducted. In the Fig. 2, a summary of the results obtained using this device is
337 presented. In the bar charts of Fig. 2, only 5 measurements, among the 15, performed on
338 each black crust area are presented to simplify the visualization of the results. Spectral
339 data were normalized in order to compare the elemental measurements performed on the
340 three measured areas. For the lighter elements (Al, Si, P, S and Cl), the net area of each
341 element was normalized against the Ca K-alpha1 line net area at 3.69 keV. The S

1 342 presence in the XRF measurements (see Fig. 2 E) confirms that these black crusts are
2 343 made up of a sulfate crust. Moreover, the normalized area of Al and Si is almost
3 344 constant in the three measured areas (BC1, BC2 and BC3) (see Fig. 2 A). The presence
4 345 of Al and Si in the black crusts could arise from the original sandstone itself or can also
5 346 suggests that aluminosilicate particles are deposited or trapped in the black crust matrix.
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7 347 This observation will be confirmed with additional measurements in the laboratory. P is
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9 348 also present in all the acquired spectra (see Fig. 2 E), suggesting the presence of
10 349 phosphates in the black crusts. Moreover, the normalized values of P are more or less
11 350 constant in the black crusts from both orientations. Considering that a Rh X-Ray tube
12 351 was used for the measurements, it is to be expected that this element L-lines cause
13 352 interference on the Cl K-lines. The software available to perform the spectral
14 353 information acquired with the hand-held instrument is not able to perform signal
15 354 deconvolutions. Therefore, in order to distinguish the contribution of Rh L-lines of the
16 355 tube from the contribution of Cl K-lines, the average net area of Rh L-alpha1 line
17 356 normalized against the Ca K-Alpha1 from different repetitive measurements (more than
18 357 10) of the instrumental blank (a Teflon block) was subtracted to the net areas of Cl K-
19 358 alpha1 line normalized against the Ca K-Alpha1. In some measurements, the
20 359 normalized value of Cl K-alpha1 area was the same of the normalized value of Rh L-
21 360 alpha1 area. Therefore, due to this interference, in these measurements, the Cl presence
22 361 cannot be ascertained. However, in some measured areas of the black crusts, this
23 362 subtraction was higher than zero, confirming the possible presence of Cl in the black
24 363 crusts (see Fig. 2 A), which was later confirmed with XRD technique.

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27 364 For the heavier elements [$Z \geq 20$ (Ca)], the net areas of their K-alpha lines were
28 365 normalized against the net area of the Rh Compton line, to correct possible matrix
29 366 effects and variations on the positioning of the measuring interface. As can be observed
30 367 in Fig. 2 B, the values of the normalized areas of Ca, Fe, Sr and Rb K-alpha lines in the
31 368 black crust from the SW orientation (BC1) and those from the SSE orientations (BC2
32 369 and BC3) are more or less in the same order of magnitude. In all the black crusts from
33 370 both orientations different metals, such as Ti, Cr, Mn, Ni, Cu, Zn and Pb were also
34 371 detected. Therefore, with the in situ elemental screening of the black crust, it can be
35 372 concluded that different kind of metals are trapped in the black crust matrix. One of the
36 373 sources of emission of these metallic particles can be the sea port of Bilbao located in
37 374 front of La Galea Fortress in the SW orientation (see Fig. 1). Moreover, in this

375 orientation, additional industries that can contribute to metallic particle emissions are
376 also located.

377 Having a look to the bar chart of Fig. 2 C and D and spectra from Fig. 2 F, a clear
378 difference in the values of Zn K-alpha line (8.6 keV), Pb L-beta line (12.6 keV), Ti K-
379 alpha line (4.5 keV), Cr K-alpha line (5.4 keV), Mn K-alpha line (5.9 keV), Ni K-alpha
380 line (7.4 keV), Cu K-alpha line (8.0 keV), and Br/As K-alpha (around 11.8 keV)
381 normalized areas are observable. The values are higher for the BC2 and BC3 black crust
382 areas from the SSE orientation, than for the BC1 black crust areas from the SW
383 orientations. This trend suggests that the metallic particles emitted by different
384 anthropogenic sources are mainly transported to the SSE orientation, thanks to the
385 influence of one of the preferential wind direction in La Galea. The presence of Ti, Cr,
386 Mn and Pb particles in the SSE orientation in La Galea Fortress was confirmed in a
387 previous works thanks to the sampling of particulate matter from the atmosphere of La
388 Galea area using a home-made passive sampler.

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390 *3.2. Characterization of black crusts in the laboratory*

391 *3.2.1 Black crusts morphology and biological colonizations*

392 The black crusts taken from both orientations are cauliflower like black crust types with
393 globular or framboidal morphology (Török, 2003; 2008) (see Fig. 3 G). In the Fig. 3 H,
394 the stratigraphy of the extracted samples is represented. As it is well-known, the first
395 step in the growing of black crusts on the surface of stones is the formation of a gypsum
396 crust. According to our previous in-depth study of La Galea Fortress sandstone, this
397 kind of stone contains around 10000 mg/Kg of calcium carbonate, thus this low
398 percentage of calcium carbonate could act as the starting nucleus of gypsum formation,
399 since calcium carbonate could be transformed into this sulfate due to the atmospheric
400 SO₂ influence. Surrounding the areas of some of the analyzed black crusts, gypsum
401 efflorescences were also identified (see those efflorescences on BC3 from the Fig. 1);
402 thus, this observation evidences that gypsum crusts could be formed on the surface of
403 this sandstone. Moreover, the joint mortar that joins together different sandstone blocks
404 could be another source of sulfates which could migrate to the porous matrix of this
405 sandstone.

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406 In the extracted black crust samples, biological patinas, biofilms or biological
407 colonizations were visually observed beneath the crust and close to the sandstone (see
408 Fig. 3 H). Different microphotographs were acquired from the samples extracted from
409 the biological patina using a Phase Contrast Microscope (see Fig. 3 A-F). The
410 microscopic observations suggest that the main colonizers on the biological patinas
411 beneath the black crusts are combined communities of cyanobacteria and green algae.
412 Concretely, the green algae present in the biofilms belong to the genera *Stichococcus*
413 (Fig. 3 A and B) and the identified cyanobacteria are from the Genus *Aphanothece* (see
414 Fig. 3 F). This kind of cyanobacteria/green algae communities can be found in stone
415 surfaces from building underside of flaking scales and on the freshly exposed stone
416 (Török et al., 2007). Therefore, in this case, the biological colonization could be
417 developed before the gypsum crust growing or also after this mineral crust formation,
418 thanks to the presence of cracks between the gypsum crust and the sandstone.

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420 *3.2.2 Elemental and molecular characterization of cauliflower like black* 421 *crusts*

422 In the Fig. 4 A, B and C, microscopic images of the BC2 black crust extracted from the
423 SSE orientation are presented as an example of the representative morphology of all the
424 sampled black crusts. These microscopic images under the SEM confirm that the black
425 crust morphology is globular or framboidal. The elemental analyses performed on the
426 acicular crystals from the black crusts using the EDS coupled to the SEM (see Fig. 4 C)
427 showed the presence of Ca, S and O (see Fig. 4 F). The X-Ray Diffraction (XRD)
428 analyses performed on those black crust samples confirmed this observation, since the
429 major component of the black crusts identified with this technique was gypsum
430 ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$). Raman results also agree with XRD observations, because gypsum
431 (bands at 414, 493, 620, 670, 1008 and 1135 cm^{-1}) was also identified in all the Raman
432 spectra acquired. Apart from that, using XRD, bassanite ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 1/2 \text{H}_2\text{O}$) and quartz
433 ($\alpha\text{-SiO}_2$) were also identified (see Fig. 4 D). This last silicate was also identified by
434 Raman spectroscopy (main band at 465 cm^{-1}). Silicon was also identified using EDS
435 (see Fig. 4 F and G). Additionally, with Raman spectroscopy in most of the spectra
436 acquired on the black crust, the D and G-bands of carbon were also identified at 1311
437 and 1599 cm^{-1} respectively (see Fig. 4 E). This carbon is the responsible of the

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438 blackened colour of the gypsum crusts. The presence of carbon was also confirmed by
439 means of EDS (see Fig. 4 F and G).

440 Considering that the limit of detections of the energy dispersive spectrometer coupled to
441 the SEM for some metals that can be trapped or accumulated in the black crusts is not
442 good enough, in order to confirm their presence, elemental maps from specific areas of
443 the black crusts were acquired using a micro energy dispersive X-Ray Fluorescence
444 spectrometer (μ -ED-XRF). In the Fig. 5 an example of the elemental mappings obtained
445 from the sample fragment of BC2 sampling area (SSE orientation) are presented. The
446 imaging analyses were performed at air, therefore elements with $Z > 15$ (Si) cannot be
447 detected. The elements identified in the mapping were Si, Cl, S, K, Ca, Ti, V, Cr, Mn,
448 Fe, Ni, Cu, Zn, Pb, As, Br, Rb, Sr and Ba. In the Fig. 5, all the elemental maps are
449 represented according to the most intense line of each element and the one which do not
450 interfere with other elements. The map of Si is not present due to the low intensity of its
451 K-alpha line in the spectra. For As and Br, their K-beta and K-alpha lines, which have
452 interference one to each other, were only detected. Therefore, the elemental maps of
453 these elements are only showed as indicative and not as conclusive results.
454 Nevertheless, as it will be explained later, the presence of Br as trace element in the
455 black crusts was confirmed using an additional laboratory ED-XRF spectrometer and
456 the application of a more suitable deconvolution process on the spectra acquired.
457 According to the obtained elemental maps, the one for Ca and S is quite coincident,
458 confirming the gypsum crust on the black crust sample (see Fig. 5). Sr, as Rb are also
459 highly distributed in the black crust. In this case, the black crust can be enriched with Sr
460 coming from marine aerosol (Whipkey et al., 2000). The distribution of Cl, Br, K, Mn,
461 V, Fe, Zn and Cr in the mapped area is more or less coincident. The first two elements
462 are present in sea salts transported by the marine aerosol (chlorides and bromides). The
463 concentration of chlorides is much higher in the marine aerosol than the one for
464 bromides (Culkin, 1965; Dyrssen and Sillen, 1967). The deposition of chloride salts was
465 also confirmed in previous studies developed in La Galea Fortress. In those works,
466 aggregate particles of Fe and Cr were identified, suggesting that both metals are emitted
467 from the same industrial source. In this case also, the elemental distribution of Fe and
468 Cr is completely coincident (see Fig. 5). In the areas where lower presence of Cl, Br, K,
469 Mn, Fe, Zn and Cr can be observed, Ba is highly accumulated. This metal can be
470 emitted to the atmosphere as particulate matter coming from the road traffic (Carrero et
471 al., 2012, 2013). Concretely, Ba together with Zn and Ti, are considered tyre wear

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472 particles. Ba, usually as barium sulfate, can also come from the brake wear, including
473 abrasion of brake lining material and brake discs, caused by grinding of brake pad
474 constituents or volatilization and condensation of brake pad material (Pant and
475 Harrison, 2013).

476 The distribution of Pb, Ti, Cu and Ni is more punctual than for the rest of the elements.
477 The first two elements were widely identified also in the airborne particulate matter
478 from La Galea atmosphere. These metals can come from the Bilbao port and thermal
479 power station emissions. Additionally, Cu and Ni, like Zn, can come from industrial
480 emissions, but also from road dust and vehicles emissions (exhaust emissions) (Pant and
481 Harrison, 2013).

482 Having this global information about the presence and distribution of different metals in
483 the black crust and taking into account the irregularities in the morphology of these kind
484 of crusts, additional punctual ED-XRF measurements were conducted in the flattest
485 surface and in the globular forms of several fragments from black crust area BC2 from
486 the SSE orientation (see results on Fig. 6). Ten repetitive measurements were performed
487 on each area using a lateral resolution of 1 mm, in order to obtain conclusions on bigger
488 areas (not so microscopic areas). Although a FP (Fundamental Parameter) based method
489 was applied to approach the concentration of each element on the measurement areas,
490 considering a possible matrix effect and the possible heterogeneous nature of the black
491 crusts, in this work the net counts offered by the data treatment software were
492 considered. In order to normalize the data, the net counts of K-lines from each detected
493 element were normalized against the K-alpha line of Rh from the tube (see results in
494 Fig. 6).

495 In both analyzed areas (see microscopic details of the measured areas on the flattest
496 surface vs. framboidal/globular forms in Fig. 6) the same elements were identified.
497 However, in the globular or framboidal forms, Cr, which was not identified in the
498 flattest surface, was also detected. The normalized counts of Ca and S are higher in the
499 flattest surface of the black crust than in the framboidal/globular forms, representing the
500 more compact gypsum matrix growing on the surface of the sandstone. The normalized
501 counts of elements like Al, K, Ti, Mn, Fe, Zr, Ni and Rb are similar in both areas of the
502 black crusts. However, the normalized counts of Si, Cl, Zn, Cu, Sr, Br, Y, V and Cr are
503 higher in the framboidal/globular forms. On the contrary, the normalized counts of Pb
504 and As are higher in the flattest surface of the black crusts.

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2 506 In order to obtain an average concentration of the elements present in all the black crust
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4 507 fragments extracted from BC1 (SW orientation), BC2 (SSE orientation) and BC3 (SSE
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6 508 orientations) samplings areas, an acid digestion of the black crust fragments followed by
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8 509 a quantification using ICP-MS was conducted. In the Table S1 from the Supplementary
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10 510 Material, the concentration of all the elements identified by ICP-MS in the acid extracts
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12 511 from the black crust are presented as an average of three repetitive samples from each
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14 512 sampling area in $\text{mg}\cdot\text{Kg}^{-1}$ units. According to the average concentration of each element
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16 513 on each sampling area (see Fig. 7), the black crusts from both orientations show more or
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18 514 less constant concentrations of Al, Na, Mg, Ca, Sb and Se. The concentrations of most
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20 515 of the metals (Fe, Sn, Ba, Pb, Ti, Mn, Co, Cu, Zn, As, Cd, V, Cr and Ni) present in the
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22 516 black crusts from the SSE orientations (BC2 and BC3) are higher, than the ones from
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24 517 the black crusts of the SW orientation (BC1). This tendency agrees with the preliminary
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26 518 observations obtained with the HH-ED-XRF device. In this sense, one of the
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28 519 preferential wind directions, the SSE, could transport the metallic particles emitted by
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30 520 the maritime port and nearby industry to the SSE orientation of the building. Therefore,
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32 521 a higher accumulation of these metals is observable in the black crusts from the SSE
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34 522 orientation. On the contrary, the concentrations of K and Sr on the black crusts from the
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36 523 SW orientation (BC1) are higher (see Fig. 7). Sr input in the black crust can be related
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38 524 with the influence of marine aerosol.

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38 526 In order to determine possible correlations between the metals identified on the black
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40 527 crusts, the Pearson correlation coefficients were calculated using the quantitative data
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42 528 obtained with the ICP-MS (see the correlation matrix in the Table S2 from the
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44 529 Supplementary Material section). Among other correlations, Pb-Sn (0.96) and Fe-Cr
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46 530 (0.90) correlations must be highlighted. In a previous work, airborne particulate matter
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48 531 was sampled in the location of La Galea Fortress. In that sampling, aggregate particles
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50 532 of Pb + Sn and Fe + Cr deposited on the passive sampler were identified. The high
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52 533 correlations obtained for both pairs of metals in the black crust reinforce the conclusion
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54 534 about a possible common origin of emission of each metal pair.

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56 536 In order to characterize the individual or aggregated particles that are trapped and
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58 537 accumulated in the black crusts from La Galea, SEM-EDS analyses were performed. As
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60 538 can be seen in Fig. 8, a different particulate matters (Fig. 8 A-F) are trapped in the black

1 539 crusts. The sizes of these visually identified particles never exceed 10 μm , thus in this
2 540 case most of the particulate matters trapped on the black crusts from La Galea location
3 541 belong to PM_{10} .

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5 543 The replicate EDS analyses (see Fig. 8 B1 and B2) performed on spherical particles
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7 544 such as the one showed in Fig. 8 A and B, showed the repetitive presence of Cl, K, O, F,
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9 545 Fe, Na, Mg, Al, S and Ca. Nevertheless, depending of the measured microscopic area,
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11 546 additional elements such as Si, Zn, Mn and Cr were observed. Therefore, a microscopic
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13 547 heterogeneous composition can be found in this kind of spherical particles.

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17 548 According to the literature, some authors point out that atmospheric SO_2 can be
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19 549 superficially absorbed on sub-spherical fly ash particles made up of Al, Si and Fe; the
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21 550 same elements that the ones identified in the spherical particle from Fig. 8 A and B. The
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23 551 S absorbed in this particles play a significant catalytic role in the black crust formation
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25 552 (Hutchinson et al., 1992; Montana et al., 2012). Apart from Cl, the F detected in the
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27 553 spherical particle could also be related with emissions coming from the marine aerosol.
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29 554 The additional metals (Fe, Zn and Cr) identified in the spherical particle can be related
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31 555 with the steelworks industries, which are placed in the Bay of Agra, close to La Galea
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33 556 Fortress.

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35 557 The EDS analyses performed on the aggregate particle from the Fig. 8 C and D showed
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37 558 the presence of K, O, Na, Mg, Al, Si, P, S, Cl, Ca, Cr and Fe. The presence of P could
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39 559 be closely related with the fuel combustion of the ships that circulate close to the
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41 560 construction. Apart from phosphorous, elements like Al, Ca, Na, Mg, K, Fe, S and also
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43 561 Li, Ti, V, Cr, Mn, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, As, Se, Rb, Sr, Cd, Sn Sb, Ba, La, Ce and Hf as
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45 562 minor and minor/trace levels could be also related with the fuel combustion (Almeida et
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47 563 al., 2005; Pey et al., 2013). In additional EDS measurements performed on the
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49 564 aggregated particle from the Fig. 8 C and D (see D4 EDS spectrum of Fig. 8), Sn was
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51 565 also detected in the particle. Sn can also be related with the steel industry and also with
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53 566 the road traffic. In an additional aggregated particle, bigger (around 20 μm) than the
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55 567 previous one (see Fig. 8 E and F), apart from the elements identified in the previous
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57 568 particles, the presence of Ti in the particle must me remarked (see EDS spectrum of the
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59 569 Fig. 8 F6). These elements can be closely related with the fuel combustion of ships from
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61 570 the Bilbao Port.

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571 In additional particles trapped in the gypsum matrix from the black crust, the presence
572 of nitrogen with additional elements was clearly observed using EDS (see Fig. 9). In the
573 same spectra, Na was also detected. Considering that in a previous work in where
574 airborne particulate matter was sampled and analyzed, particles containing sodium
575 nitrate were identified; it is possible that those particles that are present in the
576 atmosphere can be deposited on the black crust matrix. Additional sodium nitrate
577 particles were also detected in the sandstone from La Galea Fortress. As it was pointed
578 out in our previous work, sodium nitrate can be formed in the atmosphere, due to the
579 reaction between sodium chloride particles and NO_x acid aerosol present in the
580 atmosphere (Martinez-Arkarazo et al., 2007; Montana et al., 2012). Therefore, the
581 identification of this nitrate not only in the black crust matrix, but also in the sandstone
582 itself point out that the transformation process of sodium chloride particles is evident
583 and it is not an isolated example of the deposition of this kind of Secondary Marine
584 Aerosol Particles (SMAP) formed in the atmosphere and deposited in the porous
585 matrixes.

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586 Apart from N and Na, other elements were also identified in this kind of particles such
587 as Cl, K, O, Fe, Zn, Cu, Na, As, Mg, Al, Si, S and Ca. This result evidence that together
588 with SMAP, airborne particles emitted by different anthropogenic sources containing
589 metals (Fe, Zn, Cu and As in this case) can be aggregated and deposited. Remarkable is
590 also the presence of Se in this kind of particles. According to the ICP-MS results (see
591 Fig. 7), Se was identified in low concentrations. This Se can be present in the black
592 crust coming from the combustion of the fuels of the ships from the Bilbao Port (Pey et
593 al., 2013).

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594 Considering that most of the particles visualized under the SEM microscope are
595 aggregated particles, which contain different elements, it was decided to perform EDS
596 imaging on one of those representative particles in order to see all the elements
597 distribution. The particle under study was a 10 µm particle (PM₁₀) (see Fig. 10). The
598 EDS imaging study revealed the presence of O, Al, Si, Cr, Fe, Mn, Ni, S, Ti, C, Cu and
599 Ca on the particle. The Ca and S maps are coincident in a specific area, which
600 correspond with the gypsum matrix of the black crust. Apart from that, as it can be
601 observed in Fig. 10, S is also present in the particle. Si also was highly distributed in the
602 black crust matrix, suggesting the presence of quartz (α -SiO₂), which was also identified
603 using Raman spectroscopy and XRD as it has been mentioned at the beginning of this
604 work. Additionally, some areas of the Si and Al mappings are coincident, pointing out

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605 the presence of aluminosilicates in the black crust matrix (evidence also observed by
606 Raman and XRD). Regarding the metals present in the spherical particle, Cr, Fe, Mn,
607 Ni, Ti and Cu were detected (see Fig. 10). This spherical particle is a good example to
608 illustrate how the individual airborne particles do not only include a specific metal in its
609 composition. Having a look to the distribution maps, once again Fe and Cr appear
610 together, reinforcing the observation made thanks to the correlation analysis which
611 point out to a common origin of both metals. As it has been mentioned through all this
612 work, the metals distributed in this particle can come from the combustion of the fuel
613 used in the ships from Bilbao Port and also from industries near from La Galea.

614 **4. Conclusions**

615 Thanks to the multianalytical methodology applied, an exhaustive characterization of
616 the composition of black crusts present in the sandstone from the SW and SSE
617 orientations of the lighthouse keeper house from the actual La Galea Fortress was
618 performed. All the black crusts located on this building are cauliflower like black crusts
619 with globular or framboidal morphologies. The presence of gypsum crust together with
620 silicates (α -quartz and aluminosilicates) depositions and carbon particles trapped was
621 also assessed using SEM-EDS and a combination of two molecular techniques (Raman
622 spectroscopy and XRD).

623 Apart from the black crust itself, next to the sandstone and beneath the black crust, a
624 biological colonization including cyanobacteria and green algae communities, is
625 present. The cyanobacteria present belong to the Genus *Aphanothece* and the green
626 algae to the *Stichococcus* genera. Thanks to the preliminary screening with the HH-ED-
627 XRF instrument, it was possible to asses that the normalized areas from the metals
628 identified in the black crusts (Fe, Zn, Pb, Ti, Cr, Mn, Ni and Cu) were higher in the
629 black crust areas from the SSE orientation. This observation was later confirmed in the
630 laboratory using a destructive technique such as ICP-MS. The influence of marine
631 aerosol was also clearly proven since the presence of Cl and Br were identified.
632 Moreover, the elemental distribution of both elements in the black crusts is coincident,
633 suggesting the same origin for both elements. Apart from that, the distribution of Fe and
634 Cr in the black crust was more or less similar, suggesting also a common source of
635 emission for both metals. Thanks to the correlation analysis performed with the ICP-MS
636 quantitative data, a high correlation between both metals was also obtained, confirming

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637 this previous observation. This trend was also observed in previous work where
638 airborne particulate matters (aggregated particles of Fe and Cr) from the atmosphere of
639 La Galea site were sampled.

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640 The distinguished elemental characterization of both, the flattest surface or the
641 background of the black crust, and the globular/ framboidal formations at the millimeter
642 scale allowed to asses that the normalized signals arising from some metals (e.g. Zn,
643 Cu, Y, V, Cr, etc.) is higher in the globular/ framboidal formations than in the flattest
644 surface or background of the black crusts. However, it is necessary to remark that the
645 normalized signals of Pb and As in the background of the black crust were higher than
646 the ones in the globular/framboidal formations placed in the surface of the black crust
647 background. Additionally, using the quantitative data obtained by means of ICP-MS, a
648 high correlation between Pb and Sn was identified, confirming that aggregate particles
649 of Pb and Sn present in the atmosphere could be deposited and trapped in the black
650 crust matrix.

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651 The analysis of individual particles trapped on the black crust confirm that most of them
652 are PM₁₀ (10 µm size particles) and they are made up of a wide variety of elements.
653 Apart from the direct influence of marine aerosol (Na and Cl in the particles), S was
654 also identified in some particles. All the metals detected using the HH-ED-XRF and
655 additional µ-ED-XRF analyses were identified in the laboratory as constituents of the
656 particulate matter. Some of these metallic particles can come from emissions of the
657 vehicle exhaust, emissions from the fuel combustion of the ships from Bilbao Port and
658 also from the surrounding industries. Apart from that, N together with Na was also
659 detected in the trapped particles, confirming that the sodium nitrate particles that can be
660 formed in the atmosphere as Secondary Marine Aerosol particles (reaction between
661 NaCl particles and the NO_x from the atmosphere) can be deposited and also trapped in
662 the black crusts.

663 All the results extracted evidence that black crusts can be formed on sandstone with a
664 minor percentage of calcium carbonate. Moreover, the HH-ED-XRF spectrometer has
665 been proven as a promising tool to extract results regarding the metals trapped and
666 accumulated in this kind of black crusts without taking any sample, which can be
667 conclusive enough. In this case, the black crusts from the lighthouse keeper house from
668 La Galea Fortress act as collector of the emitted metallic airborne particulate matter and
669 Primary/Secondary Marine Aerosol particles. Moreover, according to all the results

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670 extracted with all the elemental applied techniques (hand-held and laboratory ED-XRF
671 instruments and ICP-MS), the black crusts from the SSE orientation showed higher
672 metals concentrations. Therefore, it can be concluded that the preferential SSE wind
673 direction transport metallic particles to the black crusts located on this orientation to a
674 greater extent than to the ones from the SW orientation.

675

676 **Acknowledgements**

677 This work has been funded by the Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness
678 (MINECO) through the project DISILICA-1930 (ref. BIA2014-59124) and the
679 Regional Development Fund (FEDER). H. Morillas is grateful to the University of the
680 Basque Country (UPV/EHU) and mainly to the action UFI 11-26 Global Change and
681 Heritage, who funded his pre-doctoral fellowship. Technical support provided by the
682 Raman-LASPEA laboratory and General X-ray General Service of the SGiker
683 (UPV/EHU, MICINN, GV/EJ, ERDF and ESF) is also gratefully acknowledged.

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820 **FIGURE CAPTIONS**

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3 821 **Fig.1.** General view of the location of La Galea Fortress and different views of the
4 822 lighthouse keeper house and the areas on it (BC1 is oriented to the Southwest and BC2
5 823 and BC3 are oriented to the Southeast) where black crusts over the sandstone were in situ
6 824 measured and extracted.

7 825
8 826 **Fig.2.** (A, B, C, D) Bar charts showing the normalized areas of all the elements found in
9 827 the black crust from the lighthouse keeper house (BC1 on the SW orientation and BC2
10 828 on the SSE orientation), (E) One representative spectrum from each black crust
11 829 analyzed showing the presence of the lightest elements and (F) One representative
12 830 spectrum from each black crust analyzed showing the presence of the heaviest elements.

13 831
14 832 **Fig.3.** A detail of the black crust from the SSE orientation (BC2) (G) and the
15 833 stratigraphy of all the extracted black crusts samples from both orientations (H),
16 834 together with the micro-photographies of the samples extracted from the biological
17 835 colonizations beneath the black crust samples from both orientations (A-F).

18 836
19 837 **Fig.4.** (A, B and C) Morphology of the studied black crust, (D) XRD spectrum showing
20 838 the presence of gypsum, bassanite and quartz, (E) Raman spectrum showing the
21 839 presence of gypsum, quartz and charcoal, (F) EDS spectrum showing the presence of
22 840 Ca, S and O belonging to gypsum, and Si, Al and C belonging to possible quartz,
23 841 aluminosilicate and charcoal and (G) EDS spectrum showing the presence of Fe, Al, Si,
24 842 Cl, Ca, S, O and P.

25 843
26 844 **Fig.5.** Accumulated spectrum obtained from the mapped area of the black crusts BC2
27 845 from the SSE orientation and maps of distribution for each element identified on the
28 846 selected area.

29 847
30 848 **Fig.6.** (A) Optical image of one of the black crusts from the BC2 sampling area (B) an
31 849 example of the microscopic appearance of the flattest areas of the black crust (C) an
32 850 example of the microscopic appearance of the globular or framboidal areas of the black
33 851 crust. On the right of the image the semi-quantitative information ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{Kg}^{-1}$) of the
34 852 elements identified in both types of formations.

35 853
36 854 **Fig.7.** Bar diagram showing the average concentration ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{Kg}^{-1}$) in logarithmic scale
37 855 for the three replicate samples of black crusts from each sampling area.

38 856
39 857 **Fig.8.** (A) General view of an spherical particle trapped in the gypsum matrix, (B) A
40 858 view of the particle in (A) using a higher magnification, (B₁, B₂) EDS spectra of the
41 859 composition of the spherical particle, (C) General view of an aggregate particle trapped
42 860 in the black crust, (D) A view of the particle in (C) using a higher magnification, (D₁,
43 861 D₂) EDS spectra of the composition of the particle in (C) and (D), (E) General view of
44 862 an additional aggregate particle, (F) A view of the particle in (E) and (F) using a higher
45 863 magnification, (F₅, F₆) EDS spectra of the particle in (E) and (F).

46 864
47 865 **Fig.9.** (A) EDS spectrum of the heterogeneous particle composed by N, Cl, K, O, Fe,
48 866 Zn, Na, Mg, Se, Al, Si, S and Ca (B) EDS spectrum of the semi spherical particle
49 867 composed by N, Cl, K, O, Fe, Zn, Cu, Se, Na, As, Mg, Al, Si, S and Ca.

50 868

869 **Fig.10.** SEM-EDS mapping showing the distribution of O, Al, Si, Cr, Fe, Mn, Ni, S, Ti,
1 870 C, Cu and Ca in a 10 µm diameter spherical particle (PM10) trapped on the black crust
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La Galea Fortress
(Getxo, Basque Country, north of Spain)

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Elements	Flattest surface	Globular/Framboidal forms
Si	0.12 ± 0.03	0.23 ± 0.04
Al	0.016 ± 0.002	0.019 ± 0.003
S	2.22 ± 0.03	1.71 ± 0.04
Cl	0.02 ± 0.01	0.11 ± 0.06
K	0.05 ± 0.01	0.059 ± 0.006
Ca	8.0 ± 0.6	6.7 ± 0.4
Ti	0.04 ± 0.01	0.04 ± 0.01
Mn	0.011 ± 0.001	0.015 ± 0.006
Fe	1.7 ± 0.5	1.8 ± 0.6
Zn	0.05 ± 0.01	0.07 ± 0.03
Cu	0.007 ± 0.002	0.015 ± 0.007
Pb	0.07 ± 0.01	0.03 ± 0.01
As	0.03 ± 0.01	0.009 ± 0.005
Sr	1.2 ± 0.1	1.9 ± 0.2
Zr	0.009 ± 0.001	0.006 ± 0.001
Ni	0.003 ± 0.002	0.004 ± 0.001
Br	0.006 ± 0.001	0.0182 ± 0.0006
Rb	0.012 ± 0.001	0.014 ± 0.001
Y	0.0002 ± 0.0001	0.005 ± 0.001
V	0.0003 ± 0.0001	0.0023 ± 0.0009
Cr	Non-detected	0.006 ± 0.002

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